

Stability Constants of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Iron(III), Cobalt(II), Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II) with Oxalic Acid as Primary Ligand and Glutathione(reduced) as Secondary Ligand

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Because of current biochemical interest¹, the present communication deals with the stabilities of mixed-ligand complexes of Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} involving oxalic acid as primary ligand and glutathione (reduced) as secondary ligand in aqueous medium at a constant ionic strength, $I=1 M$ (KNO₃) and at a constant temperature, using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti².

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constant : From the titration curves (Fig. 1), using the solutions (A) and (B), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various pH values were calculated³ and the curve between pH and the corresponding

$\bar{n}_A$ values was obtained. The formation curve extends from $\bar{n}_A=0$ to 2.5. This indicates the three-step dissociation of the ligand. The values obtained for proton-ligand stability constants are presented in Table 1.

Mixed-ligand stability constant : From the titration curves of solutions (A), (B), (C) and (D), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated and plotted (Fig. 2). It can be seen (Fig. 1) that the mixed-ligand complex curve (D) separates from the primary ligand complex curve (C) at pH 3.5 onwards due to self-dissociation of secondary ligand. After pH 3.5, mixed-ligand complex curve shows the indication of attachment of secondary ligand with metal ions.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves of [Co-OX-GSH] system.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT OF SECONDARY LIGAND AND MIXED LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT OF VARIOUS METAL COMPLEXES AT AN IONIC STRENGTH

$I=1 M$ (KNO_3), Temp. = 27°

Compd.	log K	Constant	Lit. value (25°)
Glutathione (GSH)	log K_1^H	9.9	9.65
	log K_2^H	8.4	8.75
	log K_3^H	3.1	3.59
[Fe-OX-GSH]	log K_1	4.8	—
[Co-OX-GSH]	log K_1	5.8	—
[Zn-OX-GSH]	log K_1	8.4	8.30
[Cd-OX-GSH]	log K_1	11.6	10.50

From the mixed-ligand formation curve, it is observed that $\bar{n}$ extends from 0 to 1.2, indicating that 1:1:1 complex is formed. The values for the stability constants of various complexes are presented in Table I. The stability trend of mixed ligand complexes was found to be: $Cd^{II} > Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Fe^{III}$.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade, except glutathione (reduced). A Systronics 331 pH meter with combined glass and calomel electrodes was used.

Fig. 2. Formation curves of mixed ligand complexes of glutathione.

The following solutions were prepared and titrated against standard carbonate-free KOH, keeping the total volume 50 ml at constant temperature 27° : (A) 10 ml 0.0107 M HNO_3 + 4.5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 35.5 ml H_2O , (B) 10 ml 0.0107 M HNO_3 + 1.5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 10 ml 0.01 M GSH + 28.5 ml H_2O , (C) 10 ml 0.0107 M HNO_3 + 3.0 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 10 ml 0.004 M oxalic acid + 10 ml 0.005 M metal ion + 17 ml H_2O , and (D) 10 ml 0.0107 M HNO_3 + 0.1 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 10 ml 0.01 M GSH + 10 ml 0.004 M oxalic acid + 10 ml 0.005 M metal ion + 9.9 ml H_2O .

A graph between pH and the volume of alkali added was plotted in each case (Fig. 1) for Co(OX) (GSH) system. Similar type of pH-titration curves were also observed in the case of Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} systems.

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